

CONSTITUENTS OF *CENTALLA ASIATICA*. PART I. EXAMINATION OF THE CEYLONESE VARIETY

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Centalla asiatica from Ceylon has been found to contain salts, sugar, essential oils and a nitrogen- and sulphur-containing pectin. The most characteristic components are, however, three polyhydroxy triterpenic acids, viz., centic, centoic and centellic acids, and a water-soluble glycoside, centelloside, the aglycone of which is identical with centellic acid.

The plant *Centalla asiatica*, Linn., also known as *Hydrocotyle asiatica*, occupies an important place in the indigenous system of medicine. The botanical details of the plant have been recorded by Hooker ("Flora of British India", 1879, Vol. II, p. 669) and Trieman ("Flora of Ceylon", 1894, p. 226).

Centalla asiatica has been preliminarily examined by Indian workers (Basu and Lamsal, *Quart. J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1947, 20, 135). From the Madagascar variety of the same plant, French workers isolated a crystalline, sugar ester-type triterpenoid glycoside ($C_{34}H_{54}O_{23}$, M.W. 1105.2), having a remarkable curative effect against leprosy (*Nature*, 1945, 155, 601; *Lancet*, 1945, 337; *Brit. Med. J.*, 1945, 338; Bontems, *Bull. Sci. Pharmacol.*, 1947, 49, 186; cf. Lederer *et al.*, *Nature*, 1949, 163, 258). On hydrolysis it produced two molecules of glucose, two molecules of rhamnose and a molecule of a triterpenic aglycone, asiatic acid ($C_{30}H_{48}O_8$), containing a tertiary carboxyl group and three hydroxyl groups, two of which were in the form of an α -glycol linkage. The sugar residue in the molecule was attached to the carboxyl group by an unusual ester-linkage and, in contradiction to the tertiary nature of the carboxyl group, was hydrolysed easily by both acid and alkali.

Simultaneously with the French workers, work was started by the author in the University Chemical Laboratory, Cambridge, on the Ceylonese and Indian varieties of the plant. Some of the results of investigation on the Ceylonese variety have appeared in earlier publications (*Nature*, 1949, 163, 259); details are being recorded in this communication.

The plants were collected in Ceylon and were dried in the sun before shipment; the weight of the dry plant was about 10-13% of the fresh plant. Investigation was initiated 7-8 months after collection. The plant was found to contain salts, sugars, essential oils and a large amount of pectin containing both nitrogen and sulphur which could be separated into a basic and a non-basic fraction. None of these fractions were critically examined. However, like the triterpenoid glycoside, asiaticoside, and its aglycone, asiatic acid, of the Madagascar variety, the most characteristic components of the Ceylonese samples were three monobasic, typical, tertiary-carboxyl containing polyhydroxy triterpenic acids, viz.,

1. Centic acid, $C_{30}H_{48}O_8$, three hydroxyl groups.
2. Centoic acid, $C_{30}H_{48}O_8$, four hydroxyl groups.
3. Centellic acid, $C_{30}H_{48}O_8$, four hydroxyl groups.

Most possibly, due to enzymatic hydrolysis, the seven-month old sample of the dried plant did not contain much of glycoside. However, a four-month old and sun-dried sample of the plant and also an alcoholic extract of the fresh plant were found to contain a considerable amount of a water-soluble glycoside, the aglycone of which was identical with centellic acid. This glycoside has been named as "Centelloside." As regards the other constituents, there was no fundamental difference among the various samples.

The three triterpenic acids of the Ceylonese variety were similar but different from asiatic acid, and the glycoside, centelloside, from that of asiaticoside. This has been tested by direct comparison with asiaticoside and asiatic acid. Whereas centelloside was extremely soluble in water, asiaticoside was insoluble in the same solvent. However, there were two very conspicuous points of similarity, viz., (i) Like asiaticoside, centelloside was also a sugar ester-type compound and was very easily hydrolysed by both acid and alkali.

SCHEME I

(ii) Like asiatic acid, all the three acids from the Ceylonese variety also contained an α -glycol linkage, as quantitatively estimated by specific oxidation test with potassium periodate.

The above two properties appear to be characteristic for *Centalla asiatica*, as the Indian variety has also been found to contain components with similar properties. The sugar chain in centelloside is composed of glucose and fructose; rhamnose, which is a constituent of asiaticoside, is absent. Quantitative examination of the total reducing sugars gave for centelloside the following composition: Centellic acid:glucose:fructose = 1:10:2 (mol.), suggesting an approximate molecular weight of 2660. The three triterpene acids and the glycoside, centelloside, were isolated from the alcoholic extract of the plant tissue. The outline is shown in scheme I. The glycoside, centelloside, was obtained in quantity if the plant material was not too old. The other constituents were more or less the same in different samples.

Components of Fractions A and B.—Both these fractions were composed entirely of acidic material as shown by their complete solubility in dilute alkali or alkali carbonate. Centic acid contained in fraction A was purified through its crystalline potassium salt. The free acid was however, amorphous and in this respect was similar to asiatic acid with which it was also isomeric, but not identical. Fraction B was composed of centoic acid and centellic acid. These were separated and purified as shown below :

SCHEME II

The overall yields of pure product from 1 kg. of the dried plant tissue were as follows: (i) centic acid, 0.3-0.5 g., (ii) centoic acid, 4-5 g., (iii) centellic acid, 2-3 g., (iv) centelloside from four-month old sample, 4-5 g., (v) centelloside from 1 kg. of the fresh plant, 1-2 g. Centoic acid was the major acidic component and it could also be handled comparatively easily, as its derivatives were less soluble compared to those of centellic acids. It should be noted that, possibly due to the presence of too many hydroxyl groups, the three terpenic acids and many of their derivatives, even when analytically pure, were amorphous; their melting points were also not sharp and had to be determined from a preheated bath. In combusting these materials, more time than usual was necessary to obtain concordant results. Equivalent weights could be determined accurately and were checked by parallel titrations with cholic acid. Centoic and centic acids showed correct equivalent weight; centellic acid occasionally gave anomalous results due to retention of solvent, but, doubtless, it is also represented by formula $C_{30}H_{48}O_6$.

The glycosides of *Centella asiatica* are somewhat similar in structure to the lipoids of acid-fast bacteria which are not glycerides of fatty acids but esters of fatty acids with carbohydrates (Anderson, Fortschritte der chem. Org. Naturst., Vol. III, 1948, pp. 145, 163).

EXPERIMENTAL

Aqueous extraction.—Cold aqueous extraction of the plant afforded mostly reducing sugars, salts and a small amount of pectin.

Essential oil.—The dried plant pulp (1 kg.) on steam-distillation (7 hours) yielded a steam-condensate (11 litres) which on extraction with ether and working up in the usual way furnished an essential oil (1.0 g.) with a grassy smell and which showed signs of crystallisation.

Extraction of Pectin.—The swollen plant pulp, left after removal of the essential oil, was filtered and the residue extracted by heating for one hour with two lots of water (2×5 litres). The combined extract (15 litres) after initial filtration through muslin was clarified by a supercentrifuge. It was concentrated under reduced pressure to 4 litres and diluted with absolute alcohol (8 litres). The precipitated pectin after filtration and drying at 80° - 90° weighed 79.0 g. It contained both nitrogen and sulphur. A sample of this pectin (100 g.) was subdivided with the help of HCl to a basic fraction (8.1 g.) and a non-basic fraction (1.0 g.). Both nitrogen and sulphur were present in the basic fraction.

Extraction with hot alcohol: Isolation of Triterpenic Acids & the Glycoside.—The powdered plant tissue (1 kg.) was exhaustively extracted with alcohol (8 litres) in a large stainless steel Soxhlet-type apparatus. Extraction could also be carried out by refluxing with adequate quantity (3×5 litres) of alcohol in a large round-bottomed flask. The deep green extract was initially concentrated under reduced pressure and then finally in an open basin. On cooling, a pasty semisolid residue (100-120 g.) was obtained. The residue, as such or after mixing with acid-washed sand, was then extracted continuously in a Soxhlet apparatus with petroleum (b.p. 40° - $60^\circ/60^\circ$ - 80°) for at least 6 hours. A very considerable portion of the colouring matter and most of the fatty and waxy constituents

were removed by this procedure. The residue in the thimble after drying at 60° was a hard, brittle mass (50-60 g.). After powdering, it was refluxed with absolute alcohol (2 litres) and the insoluble residue of salt and sugar (14 g.) removed by filtration. The filtrate was diluted with water to bring the strength of alcohol to about 90%. The alcoholic solution was boiled on the water-bath and to it a hot boiling solution of neutral lead acetate (40 g. in 80% alcohol, 500 c.c.) was gradually added. A thick, heavy, deep green precipitate was formed. The reaction mixture after boiling for 30 minutes was filtered hot and the precipitate on the filter bed washed with boiling 80% alcohol (500 c.c.). The green lead complex after critical examination was discarded as no useful product could be isolated from it.

From the alcoholic filtrate (3 litres), which was now only pale green in colour, excess of lead was removed as lead sulphide. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 20 minutes, filtered hot and the precipitate of lead sulphide washed with hot alcohol (200 c.c.). The combined mother-liquor was now only pale yellow in colour [if the removal of colouring matter is not complete, a second precipitation with a small amount (about 10 g.) of lead acetate may become necessary]. It was concentrated to about 2 litres and left at room temperature overnight when a slight precipitate was formed. After separation of this precipitate (0.5 g.—1.0 g. *Fraction A, centic acid*), the mother-liquor was concentrated to 50 c.c. and diluted with water (500 c.c.) when copious amount of light yellow precipitate was deposited. On cooling in the refrigerator overnight, the solid material (10-12 g. *Fraction B, centoic acid and centellic acid*) was collected by filtration. If the plant material was not too old, the mother-liquor on complete evaporation afforded the glycoside, centelloside (4-5 g.).

Treatment of Fraction A : Isolation of pure Centic Acid.—Fraction A (4 g. from 5 kg. of the plant) was dissolved in hot water (150 c.c.) containing minimum amount of caustic potash. The solution was heated to boiling and to it solid potassium chloride (15 g.) was added with stirring, when the potassium salt of centic acid crystallised out almost immediately in the form of fine needles. After leaving at room temperature overnight, the salt was collected by filtration and washed with a small amount of saturated KCl solution. Free acid was obtained by decomposition of the salt with mineral acid and further purified by precipitating it from alcoholic solution with water. The yield after drying to a constant weight at 100°/1 mm. was 1.5 g. from 5 kg. of the dried plant tissue. All measurements were made on a sample dried to a constant weight. On a preheated (220°) electrical block, centic acid softened at 230° and became semi-molten at 240° to decompose at 250°-255°. $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 38^{\circ}.1$ (EtOH; $c = 1.116$). It showed positive tetranitromethane test and usual colour reactions with sulphuric acid-nitric acid; no specific absorption in the U.V. region was found.

Equivalent weight: The following procedure was used to obtain concordant results. Centic acid (50 mg.) was dissolved in hot alcohol (20 c.c.) contained in a 100 c.c. conical flask. Boiling water (14 c.c.) was added, followed by three drops of phenolphthalein. The solution was heated to boiling and then quickly titrated to a permanent pink colour with $N/40$ -NaOH solution using a microburette calibrated to 1/100 c.c. An identical blank was run side by side. Equivalent weight was checked by determining the same

for cholic acid simultaneously. (Found: Equiv., 490.1; C, 73.60; H, 10.61. $C_{30}H_{48}O_6$ requires equiv., 488.68; C, 73.73; H, 9.90 per cent). Equiv. of cholic acid ($C_{24}H_{40}O_6$) found was 410.1 (calc. 408.56). For want of sufficient material this compound could not be examined in details. Its methyl ester, prepared by treatment of a small amount of the material in ether with diazomethane, was resistant to hydrolysis, revealing the tertiary nature of the carboxyl group.

Glycol Linkage in Centic Acid.—Dried centic acid (60.1 mg.) was dissolved by heating in dilute caustic soda (alkali 10 c. c. of $N/40$ in water, 20 c. c.) contained in a measuring flask. $N/40-H_2SO_4$ (11 c. c.) was then added when centic acid was precipitated in the form of a gelatinous mass. Sodium periodate solution (5 c. c., 0.26M) was added to the mixture and the content after shaking was left at room temperature. After 24 to 48 hours, the volume was made up to 50 c. c. and titrated in the conventional way with $N/10$ sodium arsenite solution in presence of borax-boric acid buffer; periodate consumed after 24 hours was 0.91 M; after 48 hours, 0.94 M (calc. for 1 α -glycol linkage, 1.0 M).

Treatment of Fraction B: Isolation of Centoic Acid and Centellic Acid.—Fraction B (15 g.) was dissolved in 3.5% KOH solution (300 c. c.). The filtered solution was heated to boiling and to it solid KCl (12-15 g.) was added with stirring, and the mixture set aside at room temperature for 24 hours. The potassium salt of centoic acid, which sometimes crystallised out immediately after addition of KCl, was filtered and washed with a little saturated KCl solution. The mother-liquor was kept aside for the isolation of centellic acid. Centoic acid was isolated by decomposition of potassium salt with mineral acid in aqueous suspension. The precipitate of centoic acid was washed with water and then dried at $110^\circ/2$ min. for 2 hours.

Brucine Salt of Centoic Acid.—The crude centoic acid, as obtained above, was dissolved in alcohol containing requisite quantity of brucine. On cooling in a frigidaire overnight, the brucine salt crystallised out in the form of clusters of large plates. On recrystallisation from alcohol, the optical rotation became constant. After filtration the salt was dried to a constant weight at $110^\circ/2$ mm., yield 10-11 g. from 15 g. of fraction B. On a preheated (170°) block the salt softened at 190° and gradually formed a glass; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, $+38^\circ.91$ (pyridine; $c=1.452$). (Found: C, 70.63; H, 8.50; N, 4.21. $C_{29}H_{44}O_{10}N_2$ requires C, 70.8; H, 8.3; N, 3.1 per cent).

Isolation of Pure Centoic Acid.—To the brucine salt (5 g.), dissolved in hot alcohol (50 ml.), HCl (conc., 3 c. c.) was added, followed by water (250 c. c.). The precipitate of centoic acid was filtered and washed with water. It was redissolved in a little acidulated alcohol and reprecipitated by addition of water, collected as before and dried to a constant weight at $110^\circ/2-3$ min. for 24 hours; yield 4-5 g. of the pure acid from 1 kg. of the dried plant or 7-10 kg. of the fresh plant. On a preheated block (235°) centoic acid softened at 245° and melted at $256-61^\circ$ (decomp.). It gave usual colour reactions with tetranitromethane and sulphuric acid-nitric acid; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, $+43^\circ.51$ (EtOH; $c=0.91$); $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, $+40^\circ.71$ (pyridine; $c=3.31$); no U.V. absorption.

Equivalent weight was determined as in the case of centic acid. [Found: Equiv., 504.5, 508.3, 505.0, 507.0, 509.8, 506.5, 508.0, 506.5. $C_{30}H_{48}O_6$ requires equiv., 504.68; equiv. for cholic acid found: 407.0, 406.0, 407.4, 406.3 (calc. for $C_{24}H_{40}O_6$: 408.56)]. (Found: C, 71.43, 71.84, 71.43, 71.81; H, 9.41; 10.22; 9.42; 10.32. $C_{30}H_{48}O_6$ requires C, 71.40; H, 9.60 per cent).

Methyl Ester of Centoic Acid.—Centoic acid in ethereal suspension on treatment with diazomethane in ether quickly went into solution as methyl ester. After removal of ether the methyl ester was dissolved in acetic acid, precipitated with water, filtered and dried to a constant weight at $100^{\circ}/1-2$ mm. The ester softened at 140° and gave a viscous melt at $150^{\circ}-155^{\circ}$; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, $+35^{\circ}.4$ ($c=1.046$; EtOH). (Found: C, 71.93; H, 9.78. $C_{31}H_{50}O_6$ requires C, 71.78; H, 9.72 per cent). The tertiary nature of the carboxyl group was revealed by the fact that the ester could not be hydrolysed by treatment with acid or alkali.

The Glycol Linkage in Centoic Acid.—Quantitative estimation with periodate was carried out as in the case of centic acid; periodate consumed was $1.12M$ (calc. $1.0M$).

Isolation of Centellic Acid.—The mother-liquor, left after removal of the potassium salt of centoic acid, was heated to boiling and a further quantity of solid KCl (30 g.) added to it. The small amount of the precipitate of the potassium salt of centoic acid was removed by filtration. The filtrate on acidification furnished crude centellic acid. It was purified by converting in alcoholic solution (charcoal) into its brucine salt, which on cooling in a refrigerator for 24 hours crystallised in the form of clusters of needles. Usually two crystallisations were necessary to obtain an optically pure brucine salt which, however, was much more soluble than the brucine salt of centoic acid. It was dried to a constant weight at $110^{\circ}/2$ mm., yield 2.8 g. from 3 g. of crude centellic acid. On a preheated (140°) block, the salt softened at $160^{\circ}-165^{\circ}$ and formed a glass at about 195° ; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, $-7^{\circ}.87$ ($c=3.2$; EtOH); $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, $-43^{\circ}.7$ (pyridine; $c=1.44$). (Found: C, 69.84; H, 8.52; N, 3.54. $C_{53}H_{74}O_{10}N_2$ requires C, 70.8; H, 8.3; N, 3.1 per cent).

Free centellic acid was isolated by decomposition of the brucine salt in the usual way and dried to a constant weight by heating at $110^{\circ}/2$ mm. for 24 hours; yield 2.3 g. of the pure acid from 1 kg. of the dry plant. In a preheated block (220°) it softened at 230° and melted at $234-36^{\circ}$ with decomposition. The rate of heating was an important factor. It gave usual colour reactions with tetranitromethane and nitric acid-sulphuric acid; no absorption was noticed in the U.V. region; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, $+35^{\circ}.7$ (EtOH; $c=0.94$); $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, $+32^{\circ}.1$ (pyridine; $c=3.2$); periodate consumed was 1.1 (calc. for α -glycol linkage: $1.0M$). Centellic acid is a very unusual compound; it retains water and solvent so tenaciously that it is extremely difficult to get concordant analytical results. Some of the values are recorded here. (Found: C, 70.70, 71.92, 71.75, 70.94; H, 10.10; 10.31, 10.14, 10.50. $C_{50}H_{70}O_8$ requires C, 71.40; H, 9.60 per cent). The anomalies were more conspicuous in the case of equivalent weight which varied considerably with different samples, though all of these were otherwise identical and were obtained through optically pure brucine salts. (Eq. wt. found: 533.4; 534.9, 528.0, 534.5, 533.8, 535.7, 533.4, 532.8; after six months: 524.0, 524.0; a fresh sample: 513.5, 513.7, 517.8, 519.0; another sample: 521.0, 528.2, 526.1; calc. for $C_{50}H_{70}O_8$: 504.7). [Eq. wt. of cholic acid found: 407.0, 406.0, 407.4; 402.8; 406.3, 405.9, 406.1, 411.8, 407.1; calc. for $C_{24}H_{40}O_5$: 408.56]. However, its methyl ester which had less tenacity for solvent gave better analytical results, proving conclusively that centellic acid has the formula $C_{50}H_{70}O_8$. This is also supported by the crystalline brucine salt, described earlier. The methyl ester was prepared in the usual way from the acid and diazomethane and dried at $100^{\circ}/1$ mm. as a white amorphous powder. It softened at 135° and melted at $148-53^{\circ}$;

$[\alpha]_D^{25}$, + 29°.1 (EtOH; $c=1.258$). (Found: C, 71.74; H, 10.31. $C_{21}H_{30}O_6$ requires C, 71.78; H, 9.7 per cent). The carboxyl group was tertiary, as the ester could not be hydrolysed with acid or alkali.

Isolation of Centelloside.—The glycoside was contained in the ultimate aqueous mother-liquor, left after removal of centoic and centellic acids, as indicated in scheme I. It was present only when the plant material was not too old. The glycoside-containing mother-liquor was usually deep brown in colour. On heating with mineral acid it deposited a gelatinous precipitate, showing the presence of glycoside in solution. For characterisation of the aglycone, the glycoside-containing mother-liquor (500 c.c. $\equiv$ 2 kg. of the dried plant) was mixed with H_2SO_4 (20 g. in 20 c.c. water) and boiled gently for 1 hour. There was considerable frothing during boiling and a gelatinous precipitate was formed. It was identified as centellic acid through its brucine salt ($[\alpha]_D^{25}$, -8° ; (EtOH; $c=3.2$) and through other properties. Taking the amount of attached sugar into consideration, there was about 16 g. of centelloside per kg. of the dried or 1.5 to 2.0 g. per kg. of the fresh plant.

Extraction of the fresh plant.—This extract (equivalent to 1 kg. of the fresh plant) was obtained directly from Ceylon. It had deposited a solid during transit which after separation was identified through its brucine salt as centoic acid (0.28 g.). The filtrate this time was clarified with excess of basic lead acetate according to Bontem (*loc. cit.*), and the lead-complex and the mother-liquor were separated. The mother-liquor was treated with H_2S and worked up in the usual way. It contained centelloside, the aglycone of which was characterised by Tripett and Lythgoe (*Nature* 1949, 163, 259) as centellic acid and the sugar components as glucose and fructose through paper chromatography. The lead complex was also examined by us critically. After decomposing it in alcoholic suspension with hydrogen sulphide, the alcoholic solution was found to contain a triterpene (0.32 g.) which was purified through its brucine salt and identified as centoic acid.

Asiaticoside.—The sample of this crystalline glycoside (0.5 g.), obtained from the French workers, was critically examined. It was also a sugar ester like centelloside and could be hydrolysed with both dilute acid and alkali. The aglycone, asiatic acid, obtained by hydrolysis with dilute alcoholic sulphuric acid (10 c.c. of 5% H_2SO_4 in 30% EtOH) was like the triterpene acid of Ceylonese variety and had similar properties. It had the same molecular formula as centic acid and like the latter formed a precipitate with neutral lead acetate which was not so soluble in alcohol. Centic acid, which we isolated from the Ceylonese plant pulp, presumably escaped complete precipitation with lead acetate.

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